

Learning in a Network of Distributed Environments and Resources

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What is Blender?

- 3D creation suite: animation, videogames, vfx, simulations, arch viz, sci viz, etc.
- Free/Libre Software: GNU GPL
- 1993: First lines of code
- 1995: 1.0 First version, in-house tool
- 2002: 2.25 Beginning of open source (crowdfunded)
- 2002: Blender Foundation
- Millions of downloads per year (3.4M, 2009)

And it looks like this...

Introduction

- The research project, developed within a doctoral program in Educational Technology at the University of Minho (Portugal), aims to build an understanding of **how the informal experience of knowledge contributes to the construction of formal knowledge.**
- **Theoretical framework:** Situated Cognition (Brown, Collins & Duguid, 1989), Communities of Practice (Lave & Wenger, 1991), Connectivism (Siemens, 2005), Personal Learning Environment (Attwell, 2007), Actor-Network Theory (Law, 1992) and Activity Theory (Engeström, 1987).

What?

Study the culture of "blenderheads".

Produce a detailed description of the architecture of participation and learning of the "blenderheads".

- What leadership exists? What are the sustainability factors of this open learning ecosystem?
- How to educate for the challenges presented by the future? Can we, in this landscape strongly marked by informal learning processes, find possible answers to issues such as academic inflation, lifelong learning, innovation, "long tail", etc.?

How?

The study, an **Ethnography** (Gregory, 2005), aims to produce a "**thick description**" (Geertz, 1973) of the Blender learning ecosystem, articulating its socio-technical landscape, the actors and networks, based on the **trajectories of participation and learning** of blenderheads and the **researcher's own experience**.

That's me!

1. **Semiotic Domain:** “any set of practices that recruits one or more modalities (e.g. oral or written language, images, equations, symbols, sounds, gestures, graphs, artifacts, etc.) to communicate distinctive types of meanings.” (Gee, 2003, p. 18).
2. **Affinity Group:** group of people associated with a Semiotic Domain (Gee, 2003).
3. **Network of Practice:** “networks that link people to others whom they may never get to know but who work on similar practices” (Brown & Duguid, 2000, p. 141).
4. **Affinity Spaces:** “In affinity spaces people 'bond' first and foremost to an endeavor or interest and secondarily, if at all, to each other.” (Gee, 2003, p. 98).
5. **Community of Practice:** “a unique combination of three fundamental elements: a domain of knowledge, which defines a set of issues; a community of people who care about this domain; and a shared practice that they are developing to be effective in their domain.” (Wenger, McDermott & Snyder, 2002, p. 27).
6. **Personal Learning Environment:** “A PLE is comprised of all the different tools we use in our everyday life for learning” (Attwell, 2007, p. 4).

“Learning becomes both a personal and unique trajectory through a complex space of opportunities (...) and a social journey as one shares aspects of that trajectory with others (...) for a shorter or longer time before moving on.” (Gee, 2007, p. 103).

Learning is a social activity that emerges from the path traveled by learners or novices within the community towards full participation and expertise, forming an integral and inseparable aspect of social practice.

Forums: registered members

Forums: discussion activities

	Posts p/ day		Topics p/ day		Posts p/ Topic	
	May-08	Oct-10	May-08	Oct-10	May-08	Oct-10
Blender Artists	465.8	523.0	51.0	58.8	9.1	8.9
Blend.Polis	116.2	125.7	8.8	10.7	13.2	11.8
The Blender Clan	94.8	129.8	7.5	10.3	12.7	12.6
Blender3D.cz	33.9	22.2	2.9	2.1	11.5	10.6
Blender.it	55.6	52.2	6.1	5.9	9.0	8.8
Polska Strona Blendera	19.2	13.2	2.5	1.8	7.6	7.5
G-Blender	9.0	6.7	2.2	1.6	4.1	4.3
Blenderownia	52.2	53.7	4.8	4.4	10.9	12.3
Blender Brasil	21.8	24.6	4.0	2.9	5.5	8.4
Blender PT	2.8	4.5	0.4	0.3	7.2	13.1
Blender Underground	27.3	42.8	2.4	4.1	11.2	10.5
BlenderNewbies	13.6	27.3	2.3	3.6	5.9	7.5
Pinoy Blender User Group	2.7	7.4	0.9	2.3	3.2	3.2

BlenderArtists.org

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New Posts Private Messages FAQ Calendar Community Forum Actions Quick Links Advanced Search

Forum Game Engine Game Engine Support and Discussion Platformer issues

+ Reply to Thread Results 1 to 8 of 8

Thread Tools Search Thread

23-Sep-09 04:41 #1

jinthan Member
Join Date: Feb 2009
Posts: 47

Platformer issues

I was wondering on how to do this for a long time ago, the main question is, How do I make a character stick to a moving platform without it sliding under the character. Any Ideas?

Reply Reply With Quote

23-Sep-09 07:15 #2

TheSambassador Member
Join Date: May 2008
Posts: 1,021

Friction... add a material to your platform, hit the "DYN" button, and add friction.

Reply Reply With Quote

23-Sep-09 08:12 #3

cray Member
Join Date: Dec 2008
Location: France
Posts: 559

TheSambassador

I don't think that friction is the way to go with the solutions currently available. I have found the reference object field (Motion Actuator -> Servo Control) to be a far better solution.

Note : not trying to make your argument ridiculous, or being sarcastic at all. Just trying to explain in plain english, but it's not that easy.

If the floor is slippery in a train, and if you fall, you don't fall at the speed of 300km/h : the way you move is related to the object you are standing on.
"Reference object for velocity calculation, leave empty for world reference".
Please check the attached .blend.

Friction is playing (example of the train) a relatively little part of it if we take the floor and the shoes friction properties into account. The train company doesn't put 50cm of sand in the train so people don't slide at 300km/h when they try to stand up.
That's hard to explain in english(...).

You've been using Blender for a long time and I don't, but I found that tweaking the friction settings was a solution used by a lot of "old" members, I started using Blender few months ago and I think that it's not the most relevant way to do now.

26, Filipino

Need help with this specific problem

31, USA

Here's the solution

24, French

I think there's another solution, more accurate

This is my scientific rationale

That one is an "old" solution

31, USA
Here's my legitimacy

And...

Meet Physics &
Newton!

23-Sep-09 16:42 #5

TheSambassador ◦
Member
Join Date: May 2008
Posts: 1,021

I made that Cube game 😊. All I used was Friction. Poke around with the settings... I believe I used a pretty high friction value.

Cray: Servo can work, but it pretty much requires Python, or a separate servo control for each and every different moving platform. That's why I suggested the "simple" solution.

Really, friction is all that's at work on "real life" moving platforms. When a train moves, the force of friction acts upon your shoes and moves you. If you were to jump right before a train started accelerating, you wouldn't start accelerating with the train until you landed. Moreso, if the floor of the train was 100% smooth ice with a friction coefficient of 0, when the train starts accelerating you will *literally slide in place* until you hit the back of a train, in which case the **normal force** of the train will begin to move you.

When you fall on a train going 300KPH, you *absolutely* are moving that fast... everything on the train is! However, relative to the train, you might only be going 1 or 2 KPH. When you jump on an already-moving train, you stay with the train because you're already at that velocity. If you jump OFF of a train and hit the REAL "unmoving" ground, then obviously it's going to hurt... you're going 300KPH!!!

To use friction effectively, it's a good idea to know the mathematical equations behind it:
Force of Friction = Friction Coefficient * Normal Force

And note that:
Normal Force is the force exerted back on an object (remember, "For every action there is an equal and opposite reaction."). Normal force is really just that "reaction" force. In terms of the ground, that normal force would be **Mass * Gravity**.

One thing that I wonder about though...
In actual physics, you have a **Coefficient of Static Friction** in addition to a **Coefficient of Kinetic Friction**. Blender seems to use only 1... the kinetic one (somebody correct me if I'm wrong). Might there be a way to set the first one?

-Sam

⚠ Reply Reply With Quote

24-Sep-09 07:13 #6

jlnthan ◦
Member
Join Date: Feb 2009
Posts: 47

Yes, what sambassador said was true, friction is what makes you move relative to the train, Anyway, I'll just use the friction, I think, because I'll only have a few platforms moving in one level. The game will mostly be a bop and jump platformer with a little puzzle element (note: LITTLE)

thanks for all the answers

⚠ Reply Reply With Quote

24-Sep-09 07:19 #7

jlnthan ◦
Member
Join Date: Feb 2009
Posts: 47

anyway, speed IS relative according to the theory of relativity, so we wouldn't be able to agree on how fast the guy on the train is *haha

⚠ Reply Reply With Quote

24-Sep-09 15:24 #8

cray ◦
Member

Hi,
TheSambassador
I understand your explanations and you are surely right.

What is the best way to learn?

28, Australia

Want to learn?

Do it like this...

17-Oct-10 09:47 #1

hitliu ◦
Member
Join Date: Sep 2010
Posts: 12

develop and improve the source code of blender?

Is there anyone have experience of developing of source code of blender. if i want to add some new tools for blender ,how could i do. is there some tutorials ?👉

⚠️ Reply Reply With Quote

17-Oct-10 11:07 #2

Ideasman42 ◦
Member

Join Date: Mar 2004
Location: Australia
Posts: 3,523

From time to time I see people asking about becoming a blender developer, Here is my (general) advice.
Just a note that I assume if you read this you are not a guru programmer already 😊,

Firstly blender is a big application with many different areas so the skills you need depend a lot on what area you want to work on so don't assume specific skills are needed before doing any blender development.

- Education in computer science/programming not necessary, many blender developers are self taught (including myself).
- Strong math background isn't essential, though you will probably end up learning some math along the way.

So, where to start? - many people start with some idea of what they would like to change with blender, but be prepared that it may take a while to learn enough to make these changes, so you may need to think of some easier projects and work up to this.

Firstly pick a general area you'd like to investigate and try making small changes, reading the source and generally learn how it works, this way you don't get bogged down by the fact blender has 1000's of files all this code you don't understand!.

Examples:

- * Take a python script template and modify it to do something useful.
- * Write a simple exporter to a mesh format.
- * Take an existing tool and improve it in some way.
- * Take an existing node/modifier/script/addon and use it as the basis for your own work.
- * Look at the bug tracker and try fix a bug (be really careful here, mostly the old bugs are very tricky, try looking at the newer bugs).

There are a few things that you need to be careful of when starting up.

- * If you work on projects that are not enough of a challenge it can be hard to stay motivated.
- * If you work on projects that are too complicated they may be too difficult to complete.
- * What your capable of and what you want to do probably are not on the same level, try have realistic expectations.
- * If your unsure of something, join in the #blendercoders IRC chat room or ask on the <http://lists.blender.org/mailman/listinfo/bf-committers> mailing list.
- * Don't be too disappointed if other developers are not so excited about your contribution as you'd have hoped, many developers are busy with their own projects and reviewing other peoples code is not always that simple. So you can submit a patch but depending on the scale of your work you may also try get a build on graphical and have users test to get feedback.

Tutorials

Articles

Freebies

Products

Focused Critique

How did you learn Blender?

My first week with Blender could best be described as embarrassing. I had absolutely *no idea* what I was doing. In fact, if you check my post history on blenderartists.org you can see what a true burden I was to the community:

- Rendering problems :([redbyte](#)
 - Creating faces. Is there a quicker way? [redbyte](#)
 - Texture databases? [redbyte](#)
 - Background image - can't get it to work [redbyte](#)
 - HELP WITH DUPLIFRAMES, PLEASE! (1 2) [redbyte](#)
 - 2 questions - Physics [redbyte](#)
 - Bevel Objects - HELP! [redbyte](#)
 - Mirroring - Someone sort out this out. [redbyte](#)
- *groan* Another thread by redbyte.

My learning style was the very definition of "play it by ear". I randomly floated from tutorial to tutorial, finishing some and abandoning others until I could finally create something of my own. As I recall it was a cube man.

Online Support

If you need some help on your blender project or would like to have some personal training then you can hire the Blender Support Desk.

With the screensharing software Teamviewer you can get remote support and help right on your screen. The Blender Support Desk offers online support, personal training and on-site courses for you and your staff!

→ Find out more

Services

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- + Get personal support for your projects
- + Integrate Blender into your workflow
- + Hire your own BFCT!

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The online support costs 10€ per 15 minutes. Every new client can test this service with a **free 5minute session**.

These free trial sessions will always be available for every new client!

For more information how this works check out → [this site!](#)

To request a support session fill out the form on → [this site](#)

Sintel Lite

By **BenDansie** (2 blends)

CC attribution the same as at www.sintel.org. A 'lite' version of Sintel for testing features / bugs and just general learning and experimentation.

High res, low res, fully rigged with a lighting setup.

Feedback / further info at <http://blenderartists.org/forum/showthread.php?t=206875>

I don't know when the rest of the files are getting hosted online, so DVD is still the main access to the rest of the official Durian files.

Enjoy!

Download: "sintel_lite_v2_1.blend"
[25.29 MB]

26, Australia

Rigging a Piston in Blender 2.5

22, USA

JUNE 20, 2011 | BY JONATHAN WILLIAMSON | ANIMATION, FEATURED, INTERMEDIATE, JONATHAN WILLIAMSON, TUTORIALS

In this **Blender 2.5 video tutorial** we relook at an old topic, showing how to rig a piston for automatic deformation that follows the mechanical arm.

1
tweet

retweet

This tutorial covers everything from the initial armature creation to setting up the constraints and assigning the vertex groups.

Checkout the old tutorial here: <http://www.blendercookie.com/2009/09/21/rigging-a-piston/>

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- ✓ .blend files

PURCHASE SOURCE FILES
4USD - INSTANT DOWNLOAD

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10USD/mo

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Plumbo

June 21, 2011 at 7:31 am

The piston for the arm.02 seems to be stretching, is it, or is it just an illusion?

REPLY

13

Tutee1: problem/mistake or illusion?

Tutor: mistake, I forgot to...

Tutee2: Yes you did. Adds a plus to the tutorial: what happens if you forget to...

Jonathan Williamson

June 21, 2011 at 8:59 am

13.1

I may have forgotten to disable "Inherit Scale" on the piston.02_tip and piston.02_base bones. That is what would cause the stretching.

-Jonathan

REPLY

taniwha

June 23, 2011 at 4:06 am

"Inherit Scale" is indeed the issue, not that it detracts from the quality of the tutorial. In fact, I think it adds to it: a very nice demonstration of what happens if "Inherit Scale" is forgotten.

...

16

SDGlyph

June 22, 2011 at 5:48 pm

Thanks for the tutorial, one thing I've wanted to get a grip on for a while is splitting rigs into control and deformation bones so this is a good prod in the right direction for me.

A query: you're setting up explicit bones for the pistons, which surprised me since when I've played with piston setups before I've used constraints alone to get them to work properly. It seemed quite a bit simpler. Is there an advantage one way or the other, or is it just one of those 'multiple ways of doing stuff' things?

REPLY

taniwha

June 23, 2011 at 4:11 am

16.1

Using bones allows the entire arm, pistons and all, to be one mesh. Using just constraints requires the parts to be separate objects (I've done a few that way).

I guess using constraints gives simplicity to creation, but using bones allows the whole model to be just two objects (the mesh and the armature) allowing for easier importing into other projects, though groups might help with the constraints approach.

REPLY

Tutee1: the video shows method A of rigging but I've done it in the past with method B. Which one is better?

Tutee2: A is better for this. B is better if you want to do that.

WIP – Session 86 – Old Dog Short Film – Rigging my Main Character Part 6

In this session I will set up the IK/FK setups for my arms in preparation for applying shapes to all my animation bones. Off line I sent my rig to a friend who helped me swat some bugs with the rig such as inaccurate bone names and bone axis that were not aligned properly. I will go over some of these bug swats in the next session. Source files can be downloaded [Here](#). All source files,...

RECENT WORK AND POSTS

Goal's to Live For – Jonathan Williamson's Newest Educational Release

At my age (dirt is beginning to look young), I found that I live by new goals in life. Two years ago I renewed my driver's licence and I was extended for 5 years. 'Woo Hoo', I thought, 'A new goal – live long enough

WIP – Session 86 – Old Dog Short Film – Rigging my Main Character Part 6

In this session I will set up the IK/FK setups for my arms in preparation for applying shapes to all my animation bones. Off line I sent my rig to a friend who helped me swat some bugs with the rig such as

WIP – Session 85 – Old Dog Short Film – Modeling Bib Overalls Part 2

In this session I will extrude out the sewing seams for the overalls and model the legs and finish by redoing the topology for the knees. Next session I will work on the sewing seams for the upper torso and hopefully

USA

ben amend's

BLENDER TUTORIALS

Search...

Tarantula (Free Download)

A fully rigged tarantula with particle system hairs and a basic environment.

PREVIOUS TUTORIALS

Tarantula (Free Download)

A fully rigged tarantula with particle system hairs and a basic environment.

Outdoor Lighting and Atmosphere in Blender - Overview

A brief overview of outdoor lighting and atmosphere in Blender 2.5

How to Destroy a Shed with a 'Tornado' in Blender

In this video tutorial, learn how to destroy a small shed using particles and force fields to

Archives

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tonroosendaal Ton Roosendaal

@coenspoor the Sequencer (video editor) has a smart cache, but for Image 'sequence' type it all stays in memory. Memory is cheap now!

23 Mar

tonroosendaal Ton Roosendaal

About time for a new header for blender.org! Post suggestions at BA forums: <http://bit.ly/eW9FW5> #b3d

23 Mar

tonroosendaal Ton Roosendaal

#JJAbrams on film software/vfx: "It is now democratized. Go make your movie! No community is best served when only the elite have control."

22 Mar

tonroosendaal Ton Roosendaal

Everyone: test this and feedback! <http://physbam.stanford.edu/> freshly released physics lib in BSD license. #b3d

22 Mar

coenspoor Coen Spoor

Loading a jpg sequence as a view background in #b3d 2.56 trunk causes frames to stay in memory, seen it build up to 2.7gig @tonroosendaal

23 Mar

in reply to ↑

@tonroosendaal

Ton Roosendaal

@coenspoor the Sequencer (video editor) has a smart cache, but for Image 'sequence' type it all stays in memory. Memory is cheap now!

23 Mar via web

Hannu Hoffren wins 3D World matchmove contest; with Blender + AE + others: [youtube.com/watch?v=3LiINTg...](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3LiINTg...) #b3d

25 Jun

tonroosendaal Ton Roosendaal

Blender #b3d & OS fan @francoisgfx starting at Moving Picture Company vfx London next week! Congrats :) And share us your insights!

25 Jun

tonroosendaal Ton Roosendaal

Studio|GPU switches to freeware bizz model (support/train/consult). Interesting move, still one leap away from *free* :) studiogpu.com/download/index

25 Jun

tonroosendaal Ton Roosendaal

Updated wiki page with links to progress docs by 16 #GSoC students. wiki.blender.org/index.php/Dev:... #b3d

24 Jun

tonroosendaal Ton Roosendaal

Blender proxy only allows 1 proxy per instance for speed . Just duplicate the .blends or chars and instance them each as workaround. @Laxy

24 Jun

Gilgamesh-Cycles

by Dimetrii on Apr.28, 2011, under blender, production

Привет

Сейчас я работаю над персонажем Gilgamesh. Пришлось сделать полностью новую модель и вылепить лицо. Трудно было с UV-разверткой. Но!! Пришло время рисования текстур! Много тестов с Projection Painting и слоями (diffuse, bump, specular....).

Мы встроили Cycles из исходника с помощью отличных инструкции Брехта и с помощью DingTo на blendercoders IRC. После выключения эффектов рабочего стола и второго монитора мы смогли использовать опции аппаратного ускорения (с помощью CUDA) для действительно быстрого рендеринга. Просто для удовольствия, мы добавили модели Gilgamesh и скульптуры, и создали несколько простых рендеров в Cycles, опираясь главным образом на самосветящиеся кубы в качестве источников света. Работа в этом рендере очень отличается от Blender Internal в настройке физически точных материалов с использованием нод для объединения шейдеров. Этот рендер никогда не останавливается, и если у вас есть терпение ждать, можно получить картинку с хорошим качеством. Это действительно очень быстро, если вы используете простые шейдера и рендеринг.

Для окончательного рендера Tube мы, скорее всего, будем использовать Blender Internal, так как Cycles вряд ли будет готов до завершения проекта, но это определено "тут в будущем".

Небольшой совет: использовать Cuda, вам нужна новая версия драйвера NVIDIA (270 или больше), которого нет в Ubuntu 10.10. Вы должны использовать PPA или получить ее прямо из NVIDIA.

English Version:

I am currently working on the character Gilgamesh. I had to make a completely new model and sculpt the face. It was difficult to do the UV unwrapping. But! It's time to paint textures! Many tests with Projection Painting and layers (diffuse, bump, specular).

We built Cycles from Source using Brecht's excellent instructions and with help from DingTo on blendercoders irc. After turning off Desktop effects and the second monitor we were able to use the GPU acceleration option (using Cuda) for really fast rendering. Just for fun, we brought in the Gilgamesh model and sculpt and set up some simple renders using Cycles, mainly relying on emitting cubes as light sources. Working in this renderer is very different from blender internal- you set up physically accurate

Arctic Ocean

Arctic Ocean

Greenland

Iceland

Suomi
Finland

Россия
Russia

North Pacific Ocean

North Atlantic Ocean

Kazakhstan

Mongolia

대한민국
S. Korea

Japan

Algeria

Libya

مصر
Egypt

Saudi Arabia

Iraq

Afghanistan

Pakistan

China

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Paraguay

Uruguay

Argentina

South Atlantic Ocean

DR Congo

Namibia

Botswana

South Africa

Kenya

Tanzania

Madagascar

Indian Ocean

Australia

Papua New Guinea

New Zealand

South Pacific Ocean

Southern Ocean

Southern Ocean

Antarctica

Open movies presales

2006

2008

2010

- S
- ED+BBB+S
- BBB
- ED

Last 12 months

Google Insights for Search
beta

- blender tutorial
- maya tutorial
- 3d max tutorial
- cinema 4d tutorial

2004 - present

SNOWbAll...

- Three Blender Foundation “open movies” credits lists
- Blender Foundation Certified Trainers list
- Blender Certification Review Board members
- all speakers present at the Blender Conference (2004-2010)
- current version (2.5x) developers

Affiliation network

- “Co-Affiliation as Opportunity” or “Co-Affiliation as Indicator” (Borgatti & Halgin, in press).

Next steps

- Expand Social Network Analysis.
- Select subjects for interviewing.
- Analysis of collected artifacts.
- Continue participant observation and field diary.
- Identify some boundaries: socio-technical networks and CoP.

Final thoughts

- Blender universe is expanding fast and (immigrants and natives) Education is a central concern for the natives.
- Blurring, blending, complementarity: online and offline identities, experts in X are novices in Y, social-leisure and learning activities, etc.
- Free/Libre Software (“free” as in “free speech,” not as in “free beer”) and Free Culture (CC) are two social concerns shared by the vast majority. Free and Open tools, content and processes are valued.
- Natural and daily use of a myriad of Old & New technologies to support participation and learning trajectories. Books + Twitter + DVD + YouTube + ...

Thank you!

E-mail / homepage

- [nafergo\[AT\]gmail.com](mailto:nafergo@gmail.com)
- <http://nafergo.intervir.net>

Social networks

- <http://vimeo.com/nafergo>
- <http://www.facebook.com/nafergo>
- <http://identi.ca/nafergo>
- <http://twitter.com/nafergo>
- <http://gplus.to/nafergo>
- <https://joindiaspora.com/people/36686>
- <http://www.linkedin.com/in/nafergo>